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Article · August 2022

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COMPARITIVE STUDY OF MULTISTOREY BUILDING SUBJECTED TO WIND AND SEISMIC LOADS ACCORDING TO INDIAN STANDARDS

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Abstract: In modern day situation, increase in population growth has resulted in the requirement of shelter. Hence, the construction of multistoreyed buildings has increased. For durable construction, the study of impact of wind and seismic loads on the structure becomes compulsory. In this present study, a comparison of wind and seismic for a G+8 multistorey building was analyzed by using ETABS v 18.1.1 software. The effect of lateral forces are determined by the parameters such as storey displacement, storey drift and storey shear etc.

Keywords –Storey Displacement, Storey Drift, Storey Shear.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this modern technology, due to increase in urbanization, the availability of land is less thus resulting in increase in the land cost. Hence, to overcome this problem, the solution is to prefer high rise buildings. Earthquake and wind forces are the most dangerous natural hazards causing significant loss of life and severely damaging the structure. These loads play an important role in the design of high rise structures.

Ground motions generating earthquake are the most devastating motions causing loss of life. Earthquake is not only caused by vibrations or ground motions but also by effects such as land sliding and fires. Hence, the structure must be designed for greater stability to withstand extreme and severe ground vibrations.

Wind has no pre-defined motion since it moves randomly with specific speed and thus when it hits the structure, pressure is applied on the outer surface of the structure resulting in the generation of wind forces. Wind forces depends upon the height of the structure, topography, surrounding terrain and velocity.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

- **S. Rahman , S. A. Hossain , R. Ahmed , M. H. Rahman , M. A. Hossen and J. Islam (2021)** - In this study, three different existing buildings of 8, 10 and 13 storeys are selected. The parameters considered for the study are base shear, storey shear and storey drift. The obtained results were compared for the above parameters.
- **Naveen Suthar, Pradeep K. Goyal (2021)** - In this study, a comparison of wind loads for a G+11 building for wind load as per Indian Standard Wind loads i.e., IS 875 (Part-3)-1987 and IS 875(Part-3)- 2015 is carried out. The parameters considered are the comparison of deflection and base shear. The obtained results are compared according to the above mentioned IS codes.
- **C.V.Siva Rama Prasad,Bhavani.K,Linga Raju,J,Prashanth.M (2019)** - In this study, wind and seismic loads for an elliptical shaped plan of G+12 building is carried out. The governing loads pertaining to these loads are compared for various seismic zones as per IS 1893-2016 and wind speeds as per IS 875 (Part-3)-1987 is carried out.
- **P. Shiva Kumar,M. Chandrakanth, T. Divakar, K. Srinivas Rao (2016)** – In this study, the response of multistoreyed building with different elevations such as G+5, G+11, G+23 and G+29 of regular configuration under seismic and wind loads were observed. The parameters considered for this study are storey displacements and storey drifts.

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3. STRUCTURAL MODELLING

3.1. Description of the problem

In the present situation the study of behavior of multi storey buildings under seismic and wind loads are important. These buildings may be exposed to harmful earthquakes and wind loads in the future. Hence, the identification of their performance when subjected to these lateral loads become important. The loadings are considered as per IS 875 (Part-3)-2015 and IS 1893-2016 respectively. A multi storeyed structure of G+8 is considered for the present study.

3.2. Model description

The structure is modelled and analyzed by using ETABS software. The structural and loading details of the RC structure are mentioned in Table 1. The wind and seismic loads considered for the model are mentioned in Table 2.

Table 1. Structural and loading details of the RC structure

Terms	Data
No. of storey	G+8
Size of column(mm)	300 x 600
Size of beam(mm)	200 x 600
Thickness of slab(mm)	150
Live load on slab(kN/m ²)	3 and 2
Floor finish(kN/m ²)	1
Wall loads(kN/m)	11 and 5
Grade of concrete	M25
Grade of steel	Fe500
Total height of the building(m)	25.5

Table 2. Wind and Seismic parameters

Basic wind speed(m/s)	33
Importance factor(wind)	1
Risk coefficient factor	1
Importance factor(seismic)	1.2
Response reduction factor	5
Soil type	II
Seismic zone factor(Z)	0.1(zone II) 0.16(zone III) 0.24(zone IV) 0.36(zone V)

Typical plan and 3D view of the RC framed structure in ETABS

Figure 1. Plan of RC framed structure

Figure 2. 3D Model of RC framed Structure

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Displacement

Figure 3. Storey Displacement

From the results it is observed that, storey displacement increases with the increase in seismic zone factor. Hence, zone V exhibits highest storey displacement along EQ-X and EQ-Y direction. Also, it is observed that, the storey displacement is maximum at the top storey and minimum at the bottom storey.

4.2. Storey shear

Figure 4. Storey shear

From the results it is observed that, the storey shear varies according to the different seismic zones. It is also observed that, the storey shear is maximum at the bottom storey and minimum at the top storey.

4.3. Storey Drift

Figure 5. Storey drift

From the results it is observed that, the storey drifts are within the permissible limits. Also, zone V exhibits maximum storey drift when compared to other seismic zones.

CONCLUSIONS

- The storey displacement increases with the increase in storey height and seismic zone.
- The maximum storey shear decreases with the increase in height and zone V exhibits maximum storey shear.
- Storey drift is maximum in zone V.
- The maximum storey displacement, storey shear and storey drift is found to be maximum in zone V when compared to other seismic zones since zone factor is highest for zone V.

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